

e-IRG Communiqué on the e-IRG Workshop under French EU Presidency

The e-IRG Workshop under French EU Presidency was again organised as a virtual event. Having performed 4 such successful events already and capitalising on the knowledge and experience gained, it organised its fifth and most recent one under the auspices of the French EU Presidency. This workshop, following the priorities set by the EU Presidency, conducted as a series of three webinars on the development of e-Infrastructures in the European Research Area and beyond. More specifically this webinar series covered in its first session the topic *“Towards a sustainable EOSC - The role of e-Infrastructures”*, in the second the *“Twin ‘green and digital’ transition in e-Infrastructures”*, and in the third and final session the *“Cross-e-Infrastructure collaboration and coordination (network, computing, data)”*.

In more detail, the first session, which was jointly organised with the EOSC Steering Board, aimed to raise awareness on the need for an in-depth sustainability analysis in the e-Infrastructure community. It outlined the need for e-Infrastructures to make the first steps in this area, and it helped shed light onto the current state of the EU landscape. The related presentations and discussion were followed by a breakout session where the participants faced questions intended to stimulate the participants to provide input on their own and their organisation’s views on this issue. The questions focused on unveiling the gaps in the European policy landscape, suggest elements needing care, ways to influence the national and European policy landscapes, and methods to allow the diffusion of good practices amongst MSs and ACs. The breakout session aspired that the e-IRG workshop recommendations on policies would be brought to the EOSC Steering Board for implementation.

Overall, the first session emphasised on the fact that the planned national **tri-partite events will help structure the change**, as well as **animate EOSC in the right direction**, and that there are **many good practices in different EU MSs and ACs** that need to be passed on to all other countries, so as to provide potential implementation models and ideas.

The second session focused on the urgency of the twin transition within the EU (green and digital transitions together), national and institutional e-Infrastructures. The session was intended to raise awareness on key e-infrastructure initiatives in the area along with thematic paradigms. Both the general e-infrastructure presentations, and the thematic paradigms presented aspects were significantly different than past e-IRG workshop contributions and caught the attention of all participants. More specifically, efforts to reduce the carbon footprint of IT while maintaining (and better yet increasing) efficiency, and the need for the digital transformation of the energy-sector, which will only become a reality if a human-centric approach is achieved were shown from the e-Infrastructure side. The thematic paradigms focused on views from the scientific community on issues such as digitisation, climate change and AI efforts to monitor the phenomenon, and how to avoid a dystopian future for all mankind.

Summarising the second session, it should be noted that e-infrastructure and the community overall needs to understand that **not only the energy consumption of e-Infrastructure components but also their carbon footprint have to be taken into consideration and that both need to be reduced**. Thus, it is imperative to **raise awareness amongst our peers and take actions to mitigate our effects**.

The third session aimed to address the topic of the effective collaboration and coordination of all the e-infrastructure components, i.e. networking, computing (both HTC and HPC) and data infrastructures and related services, and to reflect on some possible approaches, paradigms and impacts. This session featured a panel with representatives from some of the most active and important e-Infrastructure organisations (EOSC, GEANT, EuroHPC, EGI.eu, OpenAIRE, and EUDAT), and sparked a discussion both lively and fruitful on the need for a smooth integration process within EOSC and the need to support the researcher in his/her research efforts. Besides these organisations, there was a discussion on the KPIs across e-infrastructures and the exchange of information across various layers that already exist and could be transformed into an essential EOSC building block.

In short, the third session outlined the urgency for **more effective and better cooperation and coordination** across e-Infrastructures, which is vital for the success of all EU efforts and the provision of added value to the end user researchers. The presentations and contributions of representatives of European e-infrastructures underlined the need for a closer cooperation at the operative level, whereas other presentations emphasised that also cooperation at the policy level is a necessary precondition to address the relevant actions of the ERA policy agenda.

A solution may be **a pluggable and personalised dashboard with all artefacts/services for all researchers where all e-Infrastructures organisations will participate/contribute with interoperable services.**

The e-IRG will continue to provide policy recommendations that are also shaped by inputs provided in the e-IRG workshops and further the discussion on the e-infrastructure Commons. The upcoming e-IRG White Paper 2022 will feature the topic of the third session on better cooperation and coordination among e-Infrastructures and a set of guiding questions will be sent to the e-Infrastructure organisations for inputs.

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